

ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE SHADOWING TECHNIQUE IN ENHANCING SPEAKING AND LISTENING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the role of the shadowing technique in enhancing students' ability to listen and speak effectively. Shadowing, a language learning technique that requires simultaneous listening and repetition, is widely acknowledged for improving pronunciation, intonation, and fluency. This study involved 8th-grade students and employed a qualitative approach to evaluate their progress before and after applying the technique. Over four weeks, participants practiced shadowing exercises, after which semi-structured interviews were conducted to assess their progress in pronunciation, vocabulary and intonation. A comparison of results before and after the intervention revealed noticeable improvements in speaking abilities, highlighting students' consistent development. These findings confirm that shadowing is a valuable tool for language learners, offering an effective approach to enhancing spoken communication skills.

Keywords: shadowing technique, listening comprehension, speaking skills, pronunciation improvement, fluency development, language acquisition

Introduction

Shadowing is a language learning technique that involves listening to spoken language and simultaneously repeating it aloud. Carroll (1977) stated that shadowing was initially introduced as a training method for novice interpreters, enabling them to listen and speak simultaneously before progressing to full interpretation. It is designed to improve pronunciation, intonation, and overall speaking fluency. This approach improves listening comprehension, enriches vocabulary, and supports the development

of clearer articulation. Shadowing is widely used in language education and is particularly effective in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learning environment.

Tawil (as cited in Ahmadi & Rost, 2011) emphasized that regular exposure to the target language is essential for students to respond accurately. Rost (2011) describes shadowing as a technique in which learners simultaneously process and repeat spoken language in real time. Gilakjani and Ahmadi (2011) emphasize that listening is a crucial aspect of communication, while Rost (2011) describes it as one of the most challenging skills for foreign language learners to master. Hamada (2012) notes that in recent years, shadowing has gained attention among language instructors and has been integrated into foreign language teaching. Moreover, shadowing is frequently utilized in interpreter education, where professionals must process and articulate messages simultaneously. This technique helps learners process spoken input more effectively and improves their ability to replicate accurate pronunciation and intonation.

Passive repetition can interfere with active listening, leading students to emphasize memorization rather than true understanding. Rather than focusing on isolated words, shadowing trains learners to handle complete sentences, fostering better retention and reducing reliance on short-term memory. Kadota (2007, 2012) explains shadowing as a multi-component working memory model, with the phonological loop playing a key role in language acquisition.

A significant number of university students struggle with speaking and listening skills, highlighting the importance of adopting more effective learning strategies. Shakirov (2024) highlights that a key challenge for language learners is turning their understanding into smooth and confident speech. Although many students can identify words in reading and listening, they frequently struggle with hesitation when speaking. The shadowing technique helps bridge this gap by training the brain to process and produce language simultaneously, reducing hesitation and improving fluency in spontaneous speech.

Malekmohammad, Salehi, and Tabatabaei (2025) found that the shadowing technique significantly enhances listening comprehension across various proficiency levels, particularly among elementary and intermediate learners. Similarly, Bustos León and Loja Quichimbo (2024) demonstrated that shadowing is an effective method for improving both listening and speaking skills, making it a versatile and valuable tool for language learners.

This study seeks to determine whether the shadowing technique significantly enhances students' speaking and listening skills. Specifically, it aims to examine improvements in pronunciation, intonation, vocabulary, and coherence. The research is guided by the following questions: (1) To what extent does shadowing improve oral fluency and listening comprehension? (2) How do students perceive its effectiveness as a learning strategy?

Based on prior studies (Hamada, 2018; Ekayati, 2020), we hypothesize that students exposed to shadowing will demonstrate measurable improvements in their spoken performance.

2. Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research design to investigate the impact of the shadowing technique on students' listening and speaking skills. A pre-test/post-test approach was used to measure improvements in pronunciation, vocabulary range, coherence, and intonation before and after implementing the technique. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather qualitative insights into students' experiences with shadowing.

The study was conducted among 17 eighth-grade students (8 boys and 9 girls) selected through voluntary participation at school # 15 in Namangan city. Participants had varying levels of English proficiency, ensuring a diverse sample. They had no prior experience with shadowing, making them suitable candidates for assessing its effectiveness. Students practiced the shadowing technique over a four-week period as part of their English lessons. The intervention included:

1. **Introduction to Shadowing:** Students were introduced to the concept of shadowing, its purpose, and best practices. They watched demonstration videos explaining the technique.

2. **Video-Based Shadowing Practice:** Students watched and repeated speeches from the "English-Shadowing-Practice" YouTube channel (Video Link). These videos featured native English speakers to help students improve pronunciation and intonation.

3. **Daily Shadowing Exercises:** Each lesson included 10 minutes of shadowing practice, where students repeated speech segments in real time. They were encouraged to focus on intonation, stress, and rhythm while mimicking native speech.

4. **Independent Practice:** Students were asked to practice shadowing at home using self-selected English materials, such as podcasts or online videos.

5. Weekly Feedback Sessions: After each session, students provided verbal reflections on their experiences. Teachers monitored students' progress, offering guidance on pronunciation, pacing, and fluency.

Pre-Intervention Assessment: Before the shadowing sessions, students participated in a structured speaking test. They responded to three prompts:

1. Describe a recent event in your life. 2. Tell me about your favorite hobby. 3. Retell the following short story.

Their responses were evaluated using a 5-point rubric (1 = Poor, 5 = Excellent) in four categories: pronunciation, vocabulary range, coherence, and intonation.

Pre-Intervention Assessment Table #1

Participants	Pronunciation	vocabulary range	Coherence	Intonation	Total score
A	5	3	5	4	17
B	3	4	3	4	14
C	2	3	3	4	12
D	5	4	3	4	16
E	4	4	3	3	14
F	4	2	3	3	12
G	3	5	3	4	15
H	2	3	3	2	10
I	5	5	4	5	19
J	4	3	3	2	12
K	2	2	2	2	8
L	4	4	3	4	15
M	3	3	3	2	11
N	2	3	2	2	9
O	4	4	4	4	16
P	5	5	4	4	18
R	3	5	4	3	15

Participants	Pronunciation	Vocabulary range	Coherence	Intonation	Total score
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A	5	5	5	5	20
B	4	4	4	4	16
C	4	3	4	4	15
D	5	5	4	4	18
E	4	4	4	4	16
F	4	4	3	4	15
G	4	4	4	4	16
H	3	4	3	5	15
I	5	5	5	5	20
J	4	4	4	4	16
K	4	3	4	3	14
L	4	4	4	4	16
M	4	4	3	4	15
N	3	3	3	3	12
O	5	5	4	4	18
P	5	5	5	5	20
R	4	5	4	4	17

Note: Higher scores represent stronger performance in each category, with a maximum of 5 points per criterion and a total possible score of 20.

Post-Intervention Assessment: After four weeks of shadowing practice, students completed the same speaking test under identical conditions. Their performance was reassessed using the same rubric.

Post-Intervention Assessment Table #2

Note: Higher scores represent stronger performance in each category, with a maximum of 5 points per criterion and a total possible score of 20.

Semi-Structured Interviews: After the post-test, students participated in one-on-one interviews to share their experiences. They were asked:

1. How did shadowing affect your speaking confidence?
2. Did shadowing help improve your pronunciation and listening skills?
3. What difficulties did you encounter while practicing shadowing?

The collected interviews were carefully transcribed and analyzed to determine the effectiveness and challenges of shadowing. Participation in this study was voluntary, and students' identities remained anonymous in all published data. Parental consent was obtained for all participants. The study followed ethical guidelines for educational research, ensuring that students faced no risks during the intervention.

Summary of results

The pre-intervention analysis showed a mean score of 13.71, with a median of 14.0 and a mode of 12. The standard deviation was 3.04, reflecting moderate variability

among students. Post-intervention, the mean rose to 16.41, while the median and mode increased to 16.0 and 16, respectively. The lower standard deviation of 2.14 suggests that students' performance became more consistent.

Here is a line graph comparing the total scores of participants before and after implementing the shadowing technique.

The increase in mean (13.71 → 16.41) and median (14.0 → 16.0) indicates an overall improvement in speaking skills. The shift in mode (12 → 16) suggests more students performed consistently well, while the lower standard deviation (3.04 → 2.14) reflects reduced variability, meaning students' progress became more uniform.

The findings reveal a clear enhancement in students' speaking proficiency following the implementation of the shadowing technique. Prior to the intervention, scores ranged from 8 to 19, whereas after the sessions, they consistently improved, falling between 12 and 20. This upward trend suggests that shadowing plays a crucial role in refining pronunciation, expanding vocabulary, strengthening coherence, and improving intonation. The overall results demonstrate that shadowing is an effective approach for developing both listening and speaking skills in language learning.

Discussion

The greatest improvement was observed in pronunciation and intonation, suggesting that the shadowing technique, which involves immediate repetition of spoken language, helps students develop more natural speech patterns. Some students, especially those who had lower scores before the study, made the biggest improvements. This supports findings from Malekmohammad, Salehi, and Tabatabaei (2025), who also found shadowing to be helpful for learners at different levels.

Students found shadowing to be helpful and enjoyable. One student shared, “Shadowing helped me pronounce words naturally without overthinking,” while another said it made listening to English easier. This shows that students not only improved their skills but also gained more confidence in speaking.

Teachers can include shadowing in their lessons by using videos, podcasts, or recorded speeches. Listening to real conversations and repeating them can help students improve naturally. Using apps or online tools that offer shadowing practice may also make learning more engaging.

Limitations and Future Studies

This study had a small number of students and lasted only four weeks, so a longer study and a bigger number of students involved in the study could give more detailed results. Future research could also see if shadowing helps with enlarging vocabulary and increase fluency not only in everyday conversations but also being able to conduct public speaking, not just in structured lessons.

Conclusion

This study shows that shadowing is a simple and effective way to improve English speaking and listening skills. It enhances students' pronunciation, improves their comprehension of spoken English, and boosts their confidence in communication. Teachers should consider using shadowing exercises in their classes to help students improve naturally and make learning more enjoyable.

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